

Atmospheric Pollution Research

Chemical characterization and source apportionment of size-segregated aerosol in the port-city of Venice (Italy) --Manuscript Draft--

Manuscript Number:	APR-D-20-00840R1
Article Type:	Research Paper
Keywords:	Size-segregated aerosol; Source apportionment; PMF; ship traffic; MOUDI
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Abstract:	<p>The sources impacting size-segregated aerosol were studied in Venice (Italy), in the framework of the ECOMOBILITY project (ECOLOGical supporting for traffic Management in cOastal areas By using an IntelLIgenT sYstem, Interreg Italy-Croatia). The importance of this work lies in the fact that aerosol can have a different impact on human health, based on the particle size: nanoparticles could be potentially more dangerous with respect to coarse and fine particles; at the same time, they are poorly studied. The aim of this work is to perform an overview of the chemical composition of size-segregated aerosol, for carrying out a size-dependent source apportionment of aerosol in the urban area of Venice. Aerosol was collected with a MOUDI 110 cascade impactor. After the gravimetric analysis, filters were divided in three parts and each piece underwent a different analytical procedure, for the analysis of trace metals, carbonaceous and ionic species. Source apportionment was conducted using two different approaches: i) approximate formulae; ii) Positive Matrix Factorization. Sea spray aerosol was found mainly in the coarse fraction. The fine fraction was dominated by secondary inorganic aerosol and organic aerosol. Primary anthropogenic aerosol increased as particle dimension decreased. For the first time, the contribution of shipping emission was investigated using chemical tracers on different size ranges below 1 μm and reaching nanoparticles ($<0.1 \mu\text{m}$): the primary contribution of ship traffic was higher in fine and nanoparticles, with respect to the coarse ones, reaching the maximum value in nanoparticles (average 7% on particles mass).</p>

HIGHLIGHTS

- Chemical characterisation of aerosol was performed in 12 size ranges
- Source apportionment of Venice size-segregated aerosol was carried out
- Impact of ship traffic was studied for the first time on particles below 1 μm
- Impact of ship traffic is higher in nanoparticles compared to larger particles

Source apportionment

TITLE

Chemical characterization and source apportionment of size-segregated aerosol in the port-city of Venice (Italy)

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1 **1. Introduction**

2 Atmospheric particles interact with the clouds affecting climate (Rosenfeld et al., 2014) and have an
3 important role in the deterioration of human health, causing allergy, asthma, cardiovascular, and
4 respiratory diseases (Shiraiwa et al., 2012). The primary parameters determining the environmental and
5 health effects of aerosol particles are their concentration, size, structure, and chemical composition
6 (Pöschl, 2005). Among these characteristics, the particle size was identified as the most critical for human
7 diseases, because the smaller the particles, the deeper they can penetrate the respiratory system: particles
8 smaller than 2.5 micron may reach the alveoli whereas ultrafine or nanoparticles (<100 nm), differently
9 from fine particles, are small enough to pass from the pulmonary epithelium to the circulation. The
10 systemic translocation of nanoparticles from the lung into the blood could cause more severe damages on
11 human health, with respect to those caused by fine and coarse particles (Hoet et al., 2004). Moreover, fine
12 particles tend to be suspended in air for long periods of time and can be transported for hundreds or
13 thousands of km (Feltracco et al., 2020; Kim et al., 2015), enhancing their potential harmful effect in space
14 and time.

15 Detailed information of aerosol sources is required to understand climate impacts and health effects of
16 atmospheric aerosols, as well as to develop technologies and policies capable to mitigate air pollution in
17 urbanized areas. This is particularly important for the city of Venice (Italy). The Venice Lagoon is the largest
18 lagoon and one of the most important wetland sites in the Mediterranean Sea; it is a winter migration halt
19 and breeding area for 200,000 birds (Martin, 2010). It is an example of an ecosystem that has been
20 influenced by human interference for many years: a significant environmental risk is represented by the
21 industrial area of Porto Marghera, one of the largest in Italy (~12 km²), including chemical and
22 metallurgical works, oil-refineries and coal power plants (Masiol et al., 2010). Air quality is also affected by
23 emissions of artistic glass-making factories on the island of Murano, by the presence of both commercial
24 and industrial harbours, the urban area of Mestre, and road traffic (Gregoris et al., 2016; Rampazzo et al.,
25 2008; Rossini et al., 2001). The Venice lagoon was designated as World Heritage Site in 1987 by Unesco and
26 it is entitled Special Protection Area (SPA), as some of its sectors are Sites of Community Importance (SCI)
27 and Important Bird Areas (IBA) (Corami et al., 2020).

28 In recent years, chemical characterization of aerosol in different size ranges has been progressively more
29 studied, also by evaluating ten or twelve size ranges. In general, major ions are usually the main analysed
30 class of chemicals, followed by carbonaceous species, such as organic and elemental carbon (Barbaro et al.,
31 2019; Contini et al., 2014; Feltracco et al., 2018). Very few studies carried out a chemical characterisation of
32 aerosol analysing trace metals alone or coupled with major ions (Bernardoni et al., 2017; Masiol et al.,
33 2015; Taiwo et al., 2014). Many other studies characterised aerosol in a lower number of size ranges
34 (Dordević et al., 2012; Đuričić-Milanković et al., 2018; Kumar et al., 2019; Paatero et al., 2017; Singh et al.,

35 2016; Turšič et al., 2006). In Venice, size-segregated aerosol was previously analysed for trace metals by
36 Masiol et al. (2015) and Toscano et al. (2011), for water soluble species by Barbaro et al. (2019), but only
37 the latter work used a sampler able to extract nanoparticles from total aerosol.

38 One of the main challenging subjects addressed in this work is the assessment of the impact of maritime
39 traffic to particulate matter. Previous studies evidenced that fine and ultrafine particles are more
40 influenced by shipping emissions with respect to the coarse ones, especially during berthing periods (Viana
41 et al., 2014). Other works confirmed that maritime traffic has a higher impact to particle number
42 concentration, that is more influenced by smaller particles, with respect to mass concentration of PM_{2.5}
43 (Contini et al., 2015; Donateo et al., 2014). Further investigation is mandatory to deeply understand these
44 aspects. Viana et al. (2014) and Sorte et al. (2020) reviewed the recent studies focusing on the impact of
45 maritime traffic to particulate matter, concluding the need of further studies to characterise the particle
46 size distribution of aerosol emitted from ships, when reaching the coastal areas (Viana et al., 2014). In the
47 reviewed papers, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} are the most investigated particle fractions and only two publications
48 included the calculation of the contribution to PM₁ (Amato et al., 2009; Mazzei et al., 2008), while particles
49 in the size ranges below 1 micron have never been investigated using chemical tracers.

50 The aim of this work is to evaluate how the major sources of aerosol are impacting particles in different size
51 in the area of Venice, specifically nanoparticles, for which little is known. To reach this objective we
52 conducted a detailed chemical characterisation of aerosol collected in twelve different size ranges in
53 Venice, using a MOUDI impactor (model 110). To our knowledge this is the first work in Europe evaluating
54 simultaneously major ions, trace metals, and carbonaceous species in the same samples, in so much
55 different aerosol size ranges and the first work detailing the size-dependent contribution of primary ship
56 traffic to particles smaller than 1 micron using chemical tracers. A detailed description of carbonaceous
57 species concentration and size distribution was given in (Cesari et al., 2020), where a comparison between
58 OC and EC results obtained in Venice and Rijeka (Croatia) is reported.

59 In the present paper, a preliminary discussion of the possible sources of aerosol was conducted comparing
60 the size distribution of chemicals and investigating possible correlations among them. One of the most used
61 methods for source apportionment is the Positive Matrix Factorization (PMF) receptor model, which
62 permits both the identification of the sources and the quantification of their contribution to airborne
63 particulate. However, PMF is not always able to completely separate the sources from each other, as the
64 identification of the sources is based on common tracers: for example, when using receptor models,
65 shipping emissions generally appear mixed with other combustion sources (Viana et al., 2014). In order to
66 overcome the disadvantages of the various methods for source apportionment, in this work the
67 quantification of sources impacting on size-segregated aerosol was conducted in two ways: i) using

68 approximate equations; ii) applying PMF separating collected data in two different datasets, one for coarse
69 ($>1 \mu\text{m}$) and the other for fine and ultrafine particles ($<1 \mu\text{m}$), as previously done in Contini et al. (2014).

70 **2. Material and methods**

71 **2.1. Aerosol sampling**

72 Aerosol sampling was carried out at Sacca Fisola Island, Venice ($45^\circ 25' 42'' \text{ N}$; $12^\circ 18' 47'' \text{ E}$) which is
73 located along the Giudecca Canal, southeast of the historical centre (Figure S1). Venice and the surrounding
74 areas are heavily affected by anthropogenic activities, such as industrial emissions from the Porto
75 Marghera industrial area and traffic pollution from the nearby Mestre motorway. The sampling site is
76 influenced by ship traffic (public transport, touristic, and merchant shipping), aircraft flying to the Venice
77 Airport, and domestic heating (Stortini et al., 2009).

78 The sampling was conducted using a model 110 MOUDI cascade impactor, equipped with twelve impactor
79 plates. Sampling of atmospheric particles undergoes several artefacts, both positive and negatives,
80 including adsorption of organic vapour, nitrate volatilization, and retention of water vapour (Perrino et al.,
81 2013; Vecchi et al., 2009; Wittmaack and Keck, 2004). Fujitani et al. (2006) verified that quartz fibre filter
82 artefacts are minimal compared with aluminium foils or Teflon-membrane filter, thus we chose quartz fibre
83 filters (QFFs, Whatman, UK) as substrate. Sixteen weekly samples were collected from August to November
84 2018 (Table S1). The sampler allows separate particles with different aerodynamic diameter. The inlet of
85 the impactor has a nominal cut-off size of $18 \mu\text{m}$, and the nominal cut-off sizes of the 10 stages are: 10, 5.6,
86 3.2, 1.8, 1.0, 0.56, 0.32, 0.18, 0.10, and $0.056 \mu\text{m}$. Finally, a back-up filter collected particles with
87 aerodynamic diameter $<0.056 \mu\text{m}$. Globally, the number of collected filters was 192 (sixteen sets of twelve
88 filters). For every set of twelve sample filters, a field blank was taken by loading, carrying, and installing the
89 QFF in the instrument with the air pump turned off, obtaining globally sixteen field blanks during the
90 campaign. Analysis of blanks was carried out to evaluate eventual contamination and to calculate the
91 method limits of detection (MDL) and quantification (MQL). MDL and MQL were evaluated as 3 and 10
92 times, respectively, the standard deviation of field blanks. Before the sampling, QFFs were decontaminated
93 with a 4 h pre-combustion at 400°C in a muffle furnace. After the gravimetric analysis, QFFs were cut and
94 the single pieces underwent different treatments. A half of the filter was analysed for metals; a 1-cm^2
95 portion of the filter was analysed for elemental and organic carbon content and the remaining filter was
96 analysed for ions.

97 **2.2. Aerosol analysis**

98 **2.2.1. Gravimetric analysis**

99 Gravimetric analysis was performed using a Sartorius CP225D balance (precision ± 0.01 mg), placed inside a
100 clean room class 1000, at Ca' Foscari University, Venice. Blanks and sampled QFFs were weighed three
101 times over 24 hours, before and after the sampling, after a conditioning period of 48 hours. The balance
102 and the filters were kept at humidity controlled ($45\pm 5\%$) in a glove box, before and during the weighting
103 procedure, in order to prevent errors in the weights due to the hygroscopy of the quartz filters. Relative
104 standard deviation of the weights was always below 0.5%. The average temperature was $22\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (± 2 standard
105 deviation).

106 **2.2.2. Chemical analysis**

107 For the determination of ions and carboxylic acids, filters were extracted in ultrapure water into ultra-sonic
108 bath and then filtrated through a $0.45\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ PTFE filter. An ion chromatograph (IC, Thermo Scientific
109 DionexTM ICS-5000, Waltham, MA, USA) coupled with a single quadrupole mass spectrometer (MS, MSQ
110 PlusTM, Thermo Scientific, Bremen, Germany) was used to analyse anionic compounds: Cl^- , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} , Br^- ,
111 methanesulphonate (MSA), oxalate, malonate, succinate, malate, following the approach described
112 elsewhere (Barbaro et al., 2019, 2017). The same IC instrumentation was also used to determine cationic
113 species (Na^+ , NH_4^+ , K^+ , Mg^{2+}), using a capillary conductivity detector (Barbaro et al., 2019, 2017).

114 The determination of metals (Li, Ti, V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Ga, Ge, Se, Rb, Sr, Mo, Cd, Ba, Pb, U) in
115 aerosol was carried out by mineralization of the half of each filter and subsequent instrumental analysis
116 with ICP-MS (Inductively Coupled Plasma-Mass Spectrometry, iCAP RQ, Thermo Scientiphic). We used the
117 methodology described in Stortini et al. (2009), with the following modifications: the mixture of reagents
118 for the mineralisation step was nitric acid, fluoridric acid, and hydrogen peroxide, with a ratio of 2:1:1; the
119 temperature program for microwave mineralization consisted in a heating up to $190\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and a temperature
120 maintenance for 15 min. The calibration curves had $R^2 > 0.999$. A standard reference material (NIST 1648a)
121 was used to evaluate recoveries that ranged between 90% and 100%.

122 Determinations of OC and EC were obtained applying a thermo-optical transmittance (TOT) method for
123 charring carbon correction using a Sunset laboratory carbon analyser (Sunset Laboratory Inc., OR, USA) with
124 temperature offset correction. Punches of 1 cm^2 were analysed according to the EUSAAR2 protocol,
125 designed as the European standard procedure in the European Supersites for Atmospheric Aerosol
126 Research. The procedure is described in (Cesari et al., 2020) and Merico et al. (2019a).

127 **2.3. Data elaboration**

128 **2.3.1. Coefficients and ratios**

129 In this work, the non-parametric Spearman coefficient (ρ) was used to investigate the correlation among
130 variables, since it is not link to the normal distribution of data; the correlation was considered significant
131 when $p < 0.001$. The Mann-Whitney test was applied for comparing two sets of data of PM_{10} concentration
132 (§3.1). It allows obtaining information about the statistical difference among samples and specifically to
133 their provenience from the same data distribution or not, as a non-parametric alternative to the t-test.

134 The crustal enrichment factor (EFc) has been used to evaluate the degree of pollution emitting sources in
135 the aerosol. EFc assesses the enrichment of an element in the atmosphere by comparing its relative
136 abundance (respect to a reference element) in atmosphere and in the upper crustal soil. EFc has been
137 calculated for all analysed elements with the formula:

$$138 \quad EFc = (el/ref)_{air} / (el/ref)_{crust}$$

139 Where *el* and *ref* are the concentrations of the given element and the reference element, respectively, in
140 *air* and in the upper *crust*, considering the average upper-crust geological concentrations reported in
141 literature (Wedepohl, 1995). The reference is a typical crustal element, usually Si, Al, or Fe. In this study, Fe
142 has been chosen as reference element, in accordance with previous studies carried out in the same
143 sampling area (Contini et al., 2012; Morabito et al., 2020) and in other polluted regions (Contini et al., 2010;
144 Enamorado-Báez et al., 2015; Lyu et al., 2015; Malandrino et al., 2016; Rovelli et al., 2020).

145 If EFc value is close to 1, it shows a strong influence of the crustal component, EFc less than 10 indicates
146 that crustal soils are the more probable source of the element, $10 < EFc < 50$ indicates a contribution from
147 non-crustal sources, while $EFc \gg 100$ indicates an exceptionally enriched element.

148 **2.3.2. Estimation of sources contribution using formulae**

149 Sea salt aerosol (SSA) was estimated by the formula: $SSA = 1.176 (Cl^- (w/v) + Na^+ (w/v))$ (Perrino et al.,
150 2009). Secondary inorganic aerosol (SIA) is the sum of non-sea salt SO_4^{2-} ($nss-SO_4^{2-}$), NO_3^- and NH_4^+ mass
151 concentration (Perrino et al., 2009). Mineral dust (MD) and trace element oxides (TEO) were estimated by
152 using adapted formulas by Dabek-Zlotorzynska et al. (2019). MD was calculated as $2.42 Fe (w/v) + 1.94 Ti$
153 (w/v) . The original formula also included a contribution by Si, Ca and K, not evaluated in this work, thus the
154 contribution of MD can be underestimated. TEO was calculated using the following formula: $TEO = 1.47 V$
155 $(w/v) + 1.29 Mn (w/v) + 1.27 Ni (w/v) + 1.25 Cu (w/v) + 1.24 Zn (w/v) + 1.32 As (w/v) + 1.08 Pb (w/v) + 1.2$
156 $Se (w/v) + 1.37 Sr (w/v) + 1.31 Cr (w/v)$.

157 Elemental carbon, originated directly from combustion emissions, was considered to constitute the Primary
 158 Anthropogenic Aerosol (PAA). For taking into account organic compounds condensing from the exhaust
 159 gases onto the elemental carbon particles, the primary organic carbon (OC_{prim}) was estimated as $1.1 \times EC$
 160 (Castro et al., 1999); OC_{prim} was then multiplied by a conversion factor which estimates the average organic
 161 molecular weight per carbon weight of the measured aerosol. This factor may assume various values
 162 depending on the aerosol composition and the location of the sampling site (Perrino et al., 2009). Turpin
 163 and Lim (2001) suggested the use of 2.1 and 1.6, as conversion factors for non-urban and urban aerosol,
 164 respectively. Sacca Fisola is considered a background station in an urban area, thus we decided to use the
 165 factor 1.8, as already done in Perrino et al. (2009). The same conversion factor was used to evaluate the
 166 primary organic matter (OM_{prim}) and the organic aerosol (OA) contribution, mostly of secondary origin,
 167 starting from the non-primary organic carbon. The used formulas are summarised as follows:

$$168 \quad PAA = EC + OM_{prim} = EC + 1.8 \times OC_{prim} = EC + 1.8 \times 1.1 \times EC$$

$$169 \quad OA = 1.8 \times (OC - OC_{prim}) = 1.8 \times (OC - 1.1 \times EC)$$

170 In addition to be above mentioned sources, the contribution of ship traffic to size-segregated aerosol was
 171 estimated. Various chemicals were identified as possible markers of shipping emissions (V and Ni above all,
 172 but also Th, Pb, Zn, SO_4^{2-}) and usually tracer ratios are preferred for the identification of this kind of
 173 pollution source, when associated to modelling approaches (Viana et al., 2014), as will be done afterwards
 174 (§3.3.3). On the other hand, the calculation of tracer ratios alone does not permit a numerical
 175 quantification of the contribution of shipping to particulate matter and vanadium has been identified as the
 176 best tracer for indicating shipping emission (Mamoudou et al., 2018; Zhao et al., 2013). Thus, the primary
 177 contribution of ship traffic PM_{ship} was extracted considering only vanadium as a marker for the combustion
 178 in ships' engines, following the approach first introduced by Agrawal et al. (2009):

$$179 \quad PM_{ship} = \frac{R \cdot V}{F_{V,HFO}}$$

180 where HFO stands for Heavy Fuel Oil; V is the in-situ ambient concentration of vanadium ($ng\ m^{-3}$); $F_{V,HFO}$ is
 181 the typical V content (ppm) in HFOs used by vessels; in the absence of chemical analyses of fuel, the value
 182 of 65 ± 25 ppm was used to cover the typical range of $F_{V,HFO}$ (Cesari et al., 2014; Gregoris et al., 2016); R is
 183 the average ratio of $PM_{2.5}$ to normalized V emitted (ppm) and was estimated at 8205.8 ppm, for locations
 184 with HFO-burning ship emissions. Although this coefficient refers to $PM_{2.5}$, we used it as reference value for
 185 the assessment of the contribution of all size ranges, for comparison reasons. Thus, the calculated
 186 contribution should be considered as an approximation in its absolute value.

187 The contributions of the various sources were calculated sample by sample; the relative contribution (%)
188 was extracted dividing the absolute contribution (in concentration unit) for the collected mass of the
189 corresponding sample. For estimating the relative contribution of sources referred to fractions (total
190 suspended, coarse, fine, and ultrafine particles) and not to single stages, the sum of the contributions of all
191 the stages included in the fraction was divided by the sum of the collected aerosol mass in the stages
192 corresponding to that fraction. The same approach was adopted in the estimation of the relative
193 contributions obtained by PMF.

194 **2.3.3. Positive Matrix Factorisation**

195 Data were refined in order to obtain more robust datasets. Variables with more than 50% of values under
196 the detection limit (DL) were rejected. Values under DL were substituted by half of DL. As uncertainty, the
197 standard deviations of the method, normalized for the average sampling volumes of each campaign, were
198 used for metals and ions; the uncertainty of values under DL was 5/6 DL. Uncertainties on carbon were
199 determined accordingly to Merico et al. (2019b). Outliers have been identified based on the quartile
200 method. A discrimination between "strong", "weak", and "bad" variables has been made, according to the
201 signal to noise (S/N) ratio criterion, the residual analysis and evaluating the observed/predicted scatter
202 plots. PM was always labelled as "total variable" and therefore categorised as "weak", following the
203 approach reported in Gregoris et al. (2016). The stability of the solution and the uncertainty associated to
204 the results were estimated using the Bootstrap (BS) error estimation; rotational ambiguity was explored
205 using the displacement (DISP) error estimation. In order to individuate the right number of factors,
206 different solutions were explored and the most reasonable solution was selected based on the parameters
207 IM (maximum of the average of the scaled residual) and IS (maximum of the standard deviation of the
208 scaled residuals), together with the Q value (goodness of the fit), following the approach reported in
209 Contini et al. (2012).

210 **3. Results and discussion**

211 **3.1. Size distribution of aerosol**

212 From August to November 2018, weekly values of total aerosol concentration, calculated as the sum of all
213 stages, ranged from 19 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ to 51 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, with a median of 34 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. Particulate matter in Sacca Fisola
214 was mainly composed of coarse particles (65% of total suspended particulate) and fine particles (33%);
215 nanoparticles represented 2% of total suspended particulate (Figure S2). The median PM_{10} concentration,
216 calculated as sum of stages with particle diameters $<10 \mu\text{m}$, was 30 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ (IQR: 23-33). No significant
217 difference (p-value <0.001) was obtained by comparing with median value (30 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, IQR: 25-38) obtained
218 by the Regional Agency of Environmental Prevention and Protection of Veneto (ARPAV), in the same site
219 and period. PM_{10} concentration measured in this work was similar or slightly lower with respect to that

220 previously recorded in the same area (Contini et al., 2012; Gregoris et al., 2016), higher with respect of that
221 reported by Sulejmanović et al. (2014) in the urban area of Sarajevo (Bosnia and Herzegovina); it was much
222 lower with that measured in New Delhi (India) by Kumar et al. (2018) and in Chinese cities along the
223 western Pacific coast (Xu et al., 2015).

224 The median size distribution of particulate matter (Figure 1) showed the typical bimodal shape (Canepari et
225 al., 2019; Contini et al., 2014; Sun et al., 2013), with peaks of concentration around $6 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in the range
226 $10\text{-}3.2 \mu\text{m}$ and of $4.3 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at $1.0\text{-}0.56 \mu\text{m}$ (Table S2). Figure 1 shows a comparison of the size distribution
227 in August and November. Both distributions were bimodal, but it is evident a seasonal difference, consisting
228 in a prevalence of the fine fraction (in $\Delta c/\Delta \log D_p$), with maximum concentrations in the size range $1.0\text{-}0.56$
229 μm , with respect to the coarse one ($10\text{-}3.2 \mu\text{m}$) in the cold period; the opposite was observed in August,
230 when a peak of concentration in the coarse fraction, higher with respect to that measured in November.
231 The same trend has been observed in another city located in the Po Valley by Canepari et al. (2019).

232 **3.2. Chemical composition of aerosol**

233 Total suspended particulate (TSP) was composed of various classes of chemicals. The sum of all analysed
234 chemicals represented 41% of TSP. Specifically, 30% of TSP was composed of ionic species, 9% was
235 carbonaceous species, and 2% was trace metals. The most represented species was SO_4^{2-} (9% of TSP),
236 followed by NO_3^- and OC (8%), Cl^- (6%), and Na^+ (4%), coherently with previous works (Barbaro et al., 2019;
237 Contini et al., 2012; Gregoris et al., 2016; Stortini et al., 2009), although some of these works referred to
238 PM_{10} or $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentration. Among the analysed metals, the most present were Fe (66% of total metals)
239 and Ti (8%). The concentration of the most elements was in accordance with values found in other studies
240 regarding size segregated aerosol in continental (Jiang et al., 2015) and coastal cities (Ari et al., 2020;
241 Martins et al., 2020). The average concentrations of elements as Fe, Co, Cu, Zn, and Pb, considerably lower
242 than that found in the above mentioned works, are in accordance with a study carried out in a port-city
243 (Contini et al., 2010) and in other previous works carried out in the same area (Contini et al., 2012, 2011;
244 Masiol et al., 2012a, 2012b, 2010; Morabito et al., 2020). The relative concentration of carbon was lower
245 than that reported by Merico et al. (2019a) in Lecce (Italy), similar to that measured by Wang et al. (2015)
246 in China. The remaining part of TSP could be mineral dust, mainly constituted of oxides of various metals
247 and organic matter, including soluble and insoluble organic compounds not analysed in this work (Bressi et
248 al., 2013; Sciare et al., 2005; Yan et al., 2012). Additionally, some losses of chemicals are possible using a
249 cascade impactor, thus the concentration of some chemicals could be underestimated. As an example, in a
250 previous work by Contini et al. (2014), the loss of NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} was estimated as 35% and 19%
251 respectively, comparing MOUDI with a PM_{10} sampler.

252 Ionic species represented a relevant percentage of particulate matter in all collected size ranges, with the
253 exception of the size $<0.056\ \mu\text{m}$, where they contributed for only 3% of aerosol mass. Trace metals
254 represented from 1 to 6% of particulate mass, being maximum in the range $0.10\text{-}0.056\ \mu\text{m}$. Carbonaceous
255 species showed an increased concentration with decreasing particle size, reaching the maximum
256 contribution of 43% to particle mass in the size range $0.10\text{-}0.056\ \mu\text{m}$. Globally, particles of the coarse
257 fraction were mainly constituted of ions, with a little contribution of metal and carbon; moving towards
258 fine and ultrafine particles, ions were gradually substituted by carbonaceous species. The unexplained
259 percentage of total mass was significant in all collected size ranges. More details about the concentration of
260 ions and metals and their size distribution are reported in the Supplementary Material. A deep description
261 of OC and EC trend in these samples and of their size distribution was given in (Cesari et al., 2020).

262 **3.3. Source identification and apportionment**

263 **3.3.1. Source identification using coefficients**

264 In this study, Cl^- was almost completely distributed in the coarse fraction, because the predominant source
265 is sea salt, as suggested by the significant correlation between Cl^- and Na^+ ($\rho=0.83$, $p<0.001$). Other sources
266 of Cl^- , such as waste incineration and secondary aerosol formation, are less probable, since they usually
267 produce Cl^- in the fine fraction (Kaneyasu et al., 1999). The Cl^-/Na^+ ratio was calculable only for the coarse
268 fraction, due to the Na^+ concentration below MQL in the fine and ultrafine fractions. Median Cl^-/Na^+ ratio
269 was 1.64 w/w (range 0.68-6.96), similar to the expected value in sea water of 1.81 (McInnes et al., 1994);
270 the calculated median Cl^- depletion for the coarse fraction was 9.5%. This means that the coarse marine
271 aerosol was just emitted, contrary to what previously observed in an urban area of Venice (Barbaro et al.,
272 2019). This difference can be explained by the very closeness of the sampling site to the sea (Adriatic sea,
273 Figure S1): it was observed that at coastal locations the coarse fraction is dominated by fresh emissions of
274 sea salt (Herner et al., 2006) and that the mass ratio of Cl^-/Na^+ has a tendency to decrease as the distance
275 from the sea increases (Li et al., 2016).

276 The sources of SO_4^{2-} could be various, including both natural and anthropogenic origin. The marine
277 contribution to the SO_4^{2-} concentration was distinguished from the other sources, using the typical ratio of
278 $\text{SO}_4^{2-}/\text{Na}^+$ in the sea (0.25 w/w). nss-SO_4^{2-} , obtained as follows: $\text{nss-SO}_4^{2-}=\text{SO}_4^{2-}-0.25\text{Na}^+$ (Prodi et al., 2009),
279 represented 93% of total SO_4^{2-} , on average. nss-SO_4^{2-} size distribution was similar to that observed for MSA
280 and a significant correlation was found between the two anionic species ($\rho=0.83$, $p<0.001$). These results
281 suggest a possible marine biogenic origin for nss-SO_4^{2-} (Gondwe et al., 2003). MSA to nss-SO_4^{2-} ratio permits
282 to disentangle marine biogenic emission from other sulphur sources. The ratio found in this work varied
283 between 0.002 to 0.03 w/w, with a median value of 0.01 w/w, lower than that observed by Barbaro et al.
284 (2019) in Venice in March-April 2016 and than the typical range found in the unpolluted mid-latitudes

285 (0.06-0.12 w/w, Chen et al., 2012). A low MSA/nss-SO₄²⁻ could be due to an additional anthropogenic
286 source of nss-SO₄²⁻. The significant correlation between nss-SO₄²⁻ and V ($\rho=0.51$, $p<0.001$), typical tracer of
287 ship emissions (Viana et al., 2014) and the similar size distribution between the two variables, mainly
288 distributed in the fine fraction, suggest that, among the various sources, also ship traffic could give a
289 contribution to the concentration of SO₄²⁻ in aerosol, as reported by Healy et al. (2010) and Popovicheva et
290 al. (2009).

291 The formation of NO₃⁻ in the fine mode can be due to in-cloud processes and gas-to-particle condensation
292 of its precursors onto pre-existing particles (Barbaro et al., 2019). In the coarse mode it could generally be
293 originated in high sea salt concentration environment, reacting with NaCl and generating HCl, with a
294 consequent Cl⁻ depletion (Contini et al., 2014). In this work, little reduction in the foreseen Cl⁻ concentration
295 from sea salt was observed, compared to that previously measured in the urban area of Venice (Barbaro et
296 al., 2019). This is coherent with the size distribution of NO₃⁻ in the two sites: in that previous work, the NO₃⁻
297 concentration, expressed as $\Delta c/\Delta \log D_p$, was mainly distributed in the coarse fraction. On the contrary,
298 results obtained from Sacca Fisola Island showed a distribution shifted towards the fine fraction, confirming
299 a relevant difference in the contribution of the various sources of NO₃⁻ between the two areas.

300 NH₄⁺ showed a bimodal distribution, with contributions in the coarse and in the ultrafine fractions. In
301 aerosol it could be present in form of (NH₄)₂SO₄ ($\rho_{\text{NH}_4^+/\text{SO}_4^{2-}} = 0.73$, $p<0.001$). Results showed an excess of
302 NH₄⁺ with respect to the concentration necessary to neutralise SO₄²⁻ (Figure S7), with the possible
303 formation of secondary NH₄NO₃ ($\rho_{\text{NH}_4^+/\text{NO}_3^-} = 0.42$, $p<0.001$). NO₃⁻ could also be present in form of KNO₃; this
304 possibility is confirmed by the significant correlation between K⁺ and NO₃⁻ ($\rho = 0.53$).

305 K⁺ showed a complex distribution; its presence in aerosol can be due to different sources, such as marine
306 spray, soil-derived particles, biomass combustion and industry (Pachon et al., 2013). 84% of K⁺ was non-sea
307 salt K⁺ (nss-K⁺), calculated as $\text{nss-K}^+ = \text{K}^+ - 0.0355\text{Na}^+$ (Morales et al., 1998). Coherently, the K⁺/Na⁺ ratio in
308 aerosol samples (average: 0.060w/w; range: 0.030-0.441 w/w) was higher than the K⁺/Na⁺ ratio in sea
309 water (0.036 w/w). This evidence conducts to hypothesize that sea salt only partially contributed to the
310 concentration of K⁺ and that other predominant sources were also present.

311 To investigate the potential sources of carboxylic acids, the relationship between malonate and succinate
312 was analysed, as an indicator of the intensity of the photochemical production of dicarboxylic acids
313 (Barbaro et al., 2019). Succinic acid (C₄) can be degraded to malonic acid (C₃) through decarboxylation
314 reactions activated by radical groups -OH (Kawanaka et al., 2004). The median value of C₃/C₄ in TSP was
315 3.96 (1.8-19) w/w. Samples collected in the weeks 2-9 October and 30 October-7 November showed a C₃/C₄
316 above 10 w/w in TSP, suggesting the presence of aged aerosol while in the other samples the C₃/C₄ ratio
317 was always between 2 and 7 w/w.

318 The crustal enrichment factors of metals were calculated discriminating the size of the particles (coarse and
319 fine + ultrafine) (Figure S9). In the coarse fraction many elements have a strong influence of the crustal
320 component: Rb, Ti, Sr, Co, Ba ($E_{Fc} \approx 1$), and Mn, Ga, U, V, Li ($E_{Fc} \approx 2$). Cr, Ni, and Pb have E_{Fc} close to 10,
321 indicating that the crustal source is the more probable source of the elements. For Zn, Cu, Ge, and Cd is
322 more evident the contribution from anthropogenic sources. Se and Mo, with $E_{Fc} \gg 100$ are exceptionally
323 enriched. For all elements, excepting Cu, E_{Fc} s in the fine fractions are higher than the corresponding E_{Fc} s in
324 the coarse one. Given that high E_{Fc} s are related to anthropogenic activities, this result confirms that the
325 fine mode is more influenced by anthropogenic activities, with respect to the coarse mode.

326 **3.3.2. Source apportionment by approximate formulas**

327 Assuming that all Na^+ and Cl^- have exclusively marine origin, the contribution of SSA was calculated, as
328 reported in paragraph 2.3.2. SSA contributed on average for 12% to total suspended particulate, with a
329 distribution over the sampling period from 2.6% to 23%. The size distribution of SSA showed the maximum
330 of 30%, on average, for particles of size 18-10 μm and 10-5.6 μm . nss-SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- , and NH_4^+ (SIA)
331 contributed for 22% (range 12-40%) to total suspended particulate, on average, reaching a contribution of
332 37% (16-67%) in the dimensional range 1.8-0.56 μm . MD and TEO contributed on average for 3.3% (range
333 1.7-7.5%) and 0.4% (0.2-1.2%) to total suspended particulate, respectively. The MD size distribution was
334 bimodal, with a mode in the coarse fraction (1.8-5.6 μm) and a second one in the nano fraction (<0.1 μm),
335 whereas TEO was characterised by an incremental contribution with particle decreasing, with a peak of
336 1.6% in the range 0.1-0.056 μm . In TSP, PAA ranged from 1.1% to 5.0%, with an average of 3.4%,
337 comparable to that calculated by Perrino et al. (2009) in the background stations. No specific chronological
338 trend was observed. The PAA contribution rise with decreasing particle size, reaching the maximum value
339 of 37%, on average, at size 0.10-0.056 μm , coherent with the combustion processes emitting in the finer
340 fractions of aerosols (Cesari et al., 2020). The average contribution of OA to total suspended particulate
341 was 14% (range 9-27%), comparable to a previous work (Perrino et al., 2009). No specific chronological
342 trend was observed. The OA contribution rose with size particle decreasing, reaching the maximum value of
343 39%, on average, at size 0.10-0.056 μm .

344 In Table 1 and Figure 2, average contributions of SSA, SIA, MD, TEO, PAA, and OA are summarised and
345 shown, whereas the contributions in each sample is reported in the Supplementary Material (Figure S10). It
346 is evident that SSA was produced almost exclusively in the coarse fraction. The fine fraction was dominated
347 by SIA (30% of contribution) and OA (22%), with an increase in the contribution of PAA (7%), with respect to
348 the coarse fraction (1%). PAA increased as particle dimension decreased, being maximum in nanoparticles
349 (23% of contribution to particle mass). Nanoparticles were also characterized by a relevant contribution of
350 OA (19) and lower, but significant contributions of SIA (8%) and MD (7%).

351 The contribution of ship traffic was estimated separately from the other sources, since shipping emissions
352 could include also part of PPA and TEO. In TSP, PM_{ship} ranged from 0.2% to 2.1%, with an average of 1.2%.
353 The average PM_{ship} was below 1% for particles $>1.8 \mu\text{m}$ and rapidly increased for smaller particles, reaching
354 an average of 13% for particles between $0.10 \mu\text{m}$ and $0.056 \mu\text{m}$ (Figure 3). The contribution of PM_{ship} to
355 PM_{10} calculated from 2018 data (1.4%) was a bit lower with respect to that previously observed in Venice
356 with the same approach, within the POSEIDON project (Interreg MED 2007-2013), in the period 2009-2013
357 (Gregoris et al., 2016). The comparison between the results of POSEIDON and ECOMOBILITY projects is
358 shown in the Supplementary Information (Figure S11). In a recently published work, the calculation of the
359 impact of ship traffic to PM was assessed, in the same period and area, applying optical high-resolution
360 measurements of aerosol (Merico et al., 2020): they obtained a contribution of about 2% to PM_1 and of
361 7.4% to nanoparticles (in numerical concentration), very similar to the results of this work (2.3% on PM_1
362 and 7.0% on $PM_{0.1}$, respectively). The incremental trend of the contribution with decreasing particle size
363 was in accordance to what previously observed in various sites in Europe (Viana et al., 2014). Specifically, in
364 Europe the comparison has been conducted among PM_{10} , $PM_{2.5}$, and PM_1 , so far. In this work the
365 contribution to PM_1 was about 1.8 times higher with respect to the contribution to PM_{10} , comparable to
366 what observed in Spain (Viana et al., 2009) and Lampedusa (Becagli et al., 2012). As to our knowledge the
367 contribution of shipping traffic to nanoparticles/ $PM_{0.1}$ is not available in other sites in Europe, with the
368 exclusion of Brindisi and Rijeka, in which measurements were done limited to optical techniques (Merico et
369 al., 2020, 2016).

370 **3.3.3. Source apportionment by Positive Matrix Factorisation**

371 After the preliminary dataset refining, seventeen variables were chosen as input for the model using the
372 dataset of coarse particles and eighteen variables for the dataset of fine-nano particles. The number of
373 samples was 90 leading to datasets of 1530 and 1620 values for the coarse and the fine-ultrafine fractions,
374 respectively. The two datasets followed the suggestions of Henry et al. (1984), requiring that the minimum
375 number of samples should be the one that yields a ratio between degrees of freedom and number of
376 variables higher than 60. Moreover, they also met the requirement of Thurston and Spengler (1985), since
377 the number of samples exceeded the number of variables by a factor higher than three.

378 Variables were categorized as follows: SO_4^{2-} , MSA, Br^- , oxalate, malonate, malate, Mn, and Cu were strong
379 in both datasets; Cl^- , Mg^{2+} , Fe, and Zn were strong in the coarse particles dataset; NO_3^- , NH_4^+ , V, Ni, Rb, and
380 Ge were strong in the fine-nano dataset; NO_3^- , K^+ , Ti, V were weak in the coarse particle dataset while
381 succinate, Fe, and Zn were weak in the fine-nano dataset. S/N ratio of variables are reported in the
382 Supplementary Information (Figure S7). An uncertainty of 10% was added to all variables, in both datasets,
383 taking into account all the components of the overall input data uncertainty, as suggested in Belis et al.
384 (2014). The robustness of solutions was evaluated based on DISP and BS (number of bootstraps: 100;

385 minimum correlation R values: 0.6), following the suggestions given in the PMF User guide (US-EPA, 2014).
386 Starting from the coarse particle dataset, various solutions with different number of factors were
387 considered valid; among them, the solution with 5 factors was selected, based on the trends of the Q-value,
388 IM and IS. In the fine-nano particles run, only the solution with 5 factors was robust based on the BS and
389 DISP error estimation. BS and DISP error estimation parameters are reported in the Supplementary
390 Information (Table S9 and Table S10), together with the errors (Figure S12) for both selected runs. The
391 analysis of G-space plot performed for the factor contributions obtained from the base solutions revealed
392 no evident edges, so the factors were assumed to be linearly independent among them, in both selected
393 solutions (Figures S13 and S14). The comparison of reconstructed concentration by the PMF and the
394 measured values showed that PMF reconstructed the observed concentrations of the coarse fraction with
395 slope 0.93 and R^2 0.95 and of the fine-nano fraction with slope 0.86 and R^2 0.87 (Figure S15).

396 In Figure 4, the profiles of each factor obtained from the two datasets are reported in terms of absolute
397 and relative concentrations, with the relative contribution of the factors. The error bars represent the
398 standard deviation of the Bootstrap runs.

399 The first factor in the run from the coarse particle dataset showed high contribution of MSA, typical tracer
400 of marine biogenic emissions. The factor also showed a contribution of SO_4^{2-} and oxalate, often associated
401 to biogenic emission together with MSA, since they are all products of the algal bloom and contributed for
402 16% to total coarse particle mass. The contribution seems to be negligible for a great extent of the sampling
403 period and to rise up in the two last samples, collected in November (Figure S16). Various variables
404 contributed to the second factor, mainly oxalate, malonate, malate, and Ti. The presence of the carboxylic
405 anions links this factor to photo oxidation processes while the contribution of Ti to this factor also suggests
406 a contamination of crustal origin ($\text{EF}_c < 1$). The third factor was mainly characterised by the presence of
407 various metals of different origin, such as V, Mn, Fe, Cu, and Zn. V could be associated to heavy oil
408 combustion, Fe and Mn have generally a crustal origin, Cu and Zn are mainly associated to vehicular traffic
409 (Cesari et al., 2014) and showed $\text{EF}_c > 100$. The fourth factor was associated to sea spray, due to the high
410 contribution of Mg^{2+} , NO_3^- , and Cl^- ; it contributed for 30% to the coarse particle mass. The fifth factor was
411 characterised by Cl^- , Br^- and Ti (EF_c around 1), thus it was associated to a mixed source of sea spray and
412 crustal origin, with a contribution of 31% to PM.

413 The first factor of the run corresponding to the fine-nano fraction cannot be associated to a specific source,
414 since many variables, related to various origin, contribute to this factor. The second factor was
415 characterised by malonate, malate, SO_4^{2-} , and MSA. Carboxylic acids are mostly produced by photochemical
416 oxidation of organic precursors by ozone, OH radical, NO_x and other oxidants, but can be also produced by
417 biomass burning, fossil fuel combustion and urban traffic (Fu et al., 2013; Kawamura and Gagosian, 1987;
418 Kawamura and Sakaguchi, 1999). In addition, oxalate has been also associated to the algal bloom (Xu et al.,

419 2013), together with SO_4^{2-} and MSA, typical tracers of marine biogenic emissions. The source was labelled
420 as mix source of photo oxidation and marine biogenic emissions. The third source was characterised by a
421 high contribution of Ge and Rb, that are crustal elements, and it contributed to 13% of total mass of fine
422 and nanoparticles. The fourth factor was characterised by NO_3^- , NH_4^+ , and Zn. The presence of NH_4^+ could be
423 related to the use of nitrogen-fertilizers, while Zn is mainly related to traffic emissions. NO_3^- could be
424 associated to both sources, given that could be produced by the oxidation of NH_4^+ from agriculture and of
425 nitrogen oxides generated by traffic. The source, associated to agriculture and traffic, had a significant
426 contribution only from August to the beginning of October (Figure S17). After that moment, the
427 contribution was negligible. The last factor was characterised by V and Ni; thus, it could be associated to
428 heavy oil combustion from industrial activities or shipping emissions. The high concentration of Ni in the
429 factor (V/Ni: 0.7) suggests a relevant contribution of industrial emissions, given that heavy oil combustion
430 may be identified by the concentration ratio V/Ni of about 2.5-5 (Viana et al., 2009). Otherwise, a
431 contamination by shipping emissions in this area is expected, since the monitoring station is very close to
432 the harbour. The contribution of this factor decreased passing from summer to fall, coherent with the
433 expected trend of a ship emission source. The relative contribution of the fifth factor (7%) was higher to
434 that previously reported for shipping emissions to PM_{10} (Figure S11), suggesting finally a mixed source of
435 shipping plus industrial emission. This factor was extracted only in the fine-nano particle run, that is
436 coherent to the fact that fossil fuel combustion dominated the production of aerosol in the fine mode
437 (Masalaite et al., 2018).

438 PMF selected solutions showed some mixed sources, probably due to the variability of the datasets,
439 constituted of aerosol of twelve different size ranges. Despite that, some sources have been clearly
440 identified. Sea spray was identified only in the coarse fraction, in two different factors. The relative
441 contribution of the sea spray factor (forth factor extracted from the coarse particle dataset, 30%) was
442 higher with respect to that calculated using the approximate formula (18%) and similar to that calculated
443 by Contini et al. (2014), in Lecce (Italy) using the same approach with size-segregated data. Barbaro et al.
444 (2019), in the urban area of Mestre (Venice), identified an aged sea spray source, with contribution of 50%.
445 An interesting source to be investigated is that correlated with maritime traffic. In this work, ship traffic
446 was part of a mixed source, as often happens using PMF (Viana et al., 2014). However, that source was
447 identified only in the fine-ultrafine particles, where generally the contribution of ship traffic is higher, and
448 the chronological trend was that expected for maritime traffic emissions. The average contribution (7%)
449 was higher with respect to that calculated for PM_{10} using the formula by Agrawal et al. (2009) and similar to
450 that observed by Amato et al. (2009) in Barcelona (Spain, 8%), using PM_{10} data and the same approach.
451 Brines et al. (2019) identified ship traffic in a mixed PMF factor with secondary inorganic aerosol, with
452 contribution of 16% and 24% in different conditions, in Barcelona (Spain). Both solutions were robust, as all
453 factors were mapped and showed no rotational ambiguity (§2.3.3, Tables S17 and S18). A swap was

454 observed between the fourth and fifth factors of the solution obtained from the coarse particles dataset,
455 probably due to the common origin of Cl⁻ from sea spray; the solution from the fine-nano particles dataset
456 showed no swaps.

457 **4. Conclusions**

458 The size distribution of aerosol, and in particular of ionic species, trace metals, and carbonaceous species
459 concentration were studied from August to November 2018, in Sacca Fisola (Venice). Correlation
460 coefficients between chemicals, a comparison of the size distribution, and the calculus of enrichment
461 factors gave support to the results of the source apportionment, carried out based on two different
462 approaches. The use of approximated formulae permitted to cover the most important sources of aerosol,
463 excepting crustal emissions, not evaluated in this work, due to missing information about silicon. PMF
464 factors often represented mixed sources and, among these, marine biogenic emissions, sea spray, and
465 crustal emissions were clearly identified. Other sources, such as maritime traffic, industrial emissions,
466 agriculture, road traffic, and photochemical oxidation, were mixed.

467 Chemical characterisation of nanoparticles is not so common in literature, because of difficulties in
468 sampling and analysing so little quantity of particulate matter. With this work we faced this challenging
469 topic, evidencing how some minor sources in total particulate may instead become significant, changing
470 point of view towards size-segregated aerosol. As an example, we found out that primary anthropogenic
471 aerosol and shipping emissions increased as particle dimension decreased, being maximum in
472 nanoparticles. Source apportionment evidenced that fine and ultrafine particles are generated mainly by
473 anthropogenic activities, confirming the need of more size-segregated studies for investigating the impact
474 of human activities to air pollution.

475 **Acknowledgements**

476 This work was performed within the framework of the project “ECOLOGical supporting for traffic
477 Management in cOastal areas By using an IntelLIgenTsYstem” (ECOMOBILITY, Interreg Italy-Croatia 2014-
478 2020, grant nr. 10043082); the financial support of the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) and
479 national sources is gratefully acknowledged. The authors thank the Regional Agency for Environmental
480 Prevention and Protection of Veneto (ARPAV) for the availability of the monitoring site in Sacca Fisola; Luca
481 Sorarù and Alvisè Ardizzon for the sampling and analysis activities.

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786

787 Table 1. Average contribution of the investigated sources to size-segregated aerosol.

	SSA µg m ⁻³ (%)	SIA µg m ⁻³ (%)	MD ng m ⁻³ (%)	TEO ng m ⁻³ (%)	PPA ng m ⁻³ (%)	OA µg m ⁻³ (%)	Ship traffic ng m ⁻³ (%)
> 18 µm	0.38 (26%)	0.22 (14%)	58 (3.8%)	5.5 (0.4%)	1.0 (<0.1%)	0.05 (3.0%)	9.2 (0.6%)
18-10 µm	0.76 (29%)	0.23 (8.7%)	83 (3.4%)	7.4 (0.3%)	2.2 (0.1%)	0.18 (6.5%)	14.2 (0.6%)
10-5.6 µm	1.6 (31%)	0.49 (9.0%)	166 (3.2%)	11 (0.3%)	5.9 (0.2%)	0.46 (8.6%)	29.5 (0.6%)
5.6-3.2 µm	0.79 (14%)	0.62 (12%)	282 (5.4%)	18 (0.4%)	21 (0.4%)	0.63 (12%)	33.3 (0.6%)
3.2-1.8 µm	0.15 (5.2%)	0.64 (21%)	157 (5.5%)	14 (0.4%)	40 (1.5%)	0.31 (11%)	20.3 (0.7%)
1.8-1.0 µm	0.04 (0.93%)	1.8 (37%)	87 (2.9%)	17 (0.5%)	180 (5.0%)	0.59 (17%)	43.3 (1.2%)
1.0-0.56 µm	0.03 (0.66%)	2.0 (36%)	63 (1.6%)	17 (0.4%)	208 (4.5%)	0.96 (20%)	59.9 (1.3%)
0.56-0.32 µm	<0.01 (0.14%)	1.0 (32%)	33 (1.2%)	12 (0.4%)	228 (8.1%)	0.86 (27%)	72.2 (2.4%)
0.32-0.18 µm	<0.01 (0.11%)	0.48 (22%)	25 (1.3%)	9.3 (0.5%)	216 (12%)	0.48 (23%)	77.0 (3.8%)
0.18-0.10 µm	-	0.15 (16%)	19 (3.9%)	5.1 (1.0%)	146 (21%)	0.28 (35%)	43.2 (5.3%)
0.10-0.056 µm	0.02 (4.1%)	0.03 (12%)	23 (6.6%)	4.5 (1.6%)	88 (37%)	0.10 (39%)	27.9 (13%)
<0.056 µm	-	0.02 (6.4%)	22 (4.5%)	4.2 (1.0%)	81 (19%)	0.06 (14%)	13.4 (4.7%)
Coarse fraction	3.7 (18%)	3.8 (17%)	834 (4.3%)	73 (0.4%)	232 (1.1%)	2.1 (10%)	140 (0.7%)
Fine fraction	0.04 (0.3%)	3.4 (30%)	140 (1.4%)	43 (0.4%)	749 (7.4%)	2.4 (22%)	229 (2.6%)
Ultrafine fraction	0.01 (1.0%)	0.04 (8.1%)	45 (7.4%)	8.7 (1.6%)	131 (23%)	0.13 (19%)	0.03 (7.0%)
TSP	3.8 (12%)	7.2 (21%)	1019 (3.3%)	124 (0.4%)	1096 (3.4%)	4.6 (14%)	390 (1.2%)

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789 Figure 1. Aerosol size distribution in August and November 2018.

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792 Figure 2. Percentage contribution of the following sources: sea salt aerosol (SSA), secondary inorganic
 793 aerosol (SIA), mineral dust (MD), trace element oxides (TEO), primary anthropogenic aerosol (PAA), and OA
 794 (organic aerosol).

Coarse fraction

Fine fraction

Ultrafine fraction

795

796 Figure 3. Primary contribution of ship traffic to PM. The line and the box represent the mean and the
797 interquartile range, respectively.

798

799 Figure 4. Source profile for a) coarse particles and b) fine and nano particles by PMF. Absolute
 800 concentration is represented by the blue bars and the relative concentration are the red points. Errors
 801 calculated by Bootstrap are reported as error bars. Pie charts represent the relative contribution of the
 802 factors to PM mass in c) coarse particles; d) fine and nano particles.

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Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

CRedit author statement

E. Gregoris: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Writing – Original Draft, Visualisation, Project administration.

E. Morabito: Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – Original Draft. **E. Barbaro:** Investigation, Writing – Review & Editing. **M. Feltracco:** Investigation, Writing – Review & Editing. **G. Toscano:** Resources. **E. Merico:** Investigation. **F. M. Grasso:** Investigation. **D. Cesari:** Investigation. **M. Conte:** Investigation. **D. Contini:** Project administration. **A. Gambaro:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Funding acquisition.